

Hydrogen Economy has arrived on the Road. It's driving already.

Pioneering long-distance business travel with a hydrogen fuel cell electric vehicle in 2016/2017 in Europe

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Abstract: Experience and technical details of the long distance cruise with a hydrogen powered fuel cell electric vehicle (FCEV) is reported. Specifically, a Hyundai ix35 sports utility type vehicle was driven for business travel in Switzerland, Germany, Belgium, France and Luxembourg where only a limited number of hydrogen filling stations were available. Cruise was carried out as business travel by a scientist who is not an automotive engineer. The largest distance was 850 km from Zürich in Switzerland to Berlin in Germany and required nominally only one intermediate stop for hydrogen refill of 4.8 kg, which takes only 3 minutes to complete. The currently still lacking dense network of H₂ filling stations makes long distance trips to some extent and adventurous exploration. But the H₂ network is growing, and car manufacturers continue to bring more FCEV on the market. While the hydrogen economy is becoming reality, driving a FCEV is becoming less and less avant-gardist.

1 INTRODUCTION

The overwhelming majority of automobiles are driven with combustion engines which are powered by liquid fossil fuels. The combustion engines explode hydrocarbon fuels with oxygen from the ambient air. The energy from the explosion is transmitted with the engine pistons to a transmission gear system to the wheels which drive the train. The products from the chemical reaction in the combustion are in the ideal case CO₂ and H₂O. In practice, other reaction products such as CO, NO_x, carbonaceous soot and SO₂ may form depending on fuel composition and driving conditions.

Carnot's principle dictates that the thermodynamic efficiency of a motor which converts the heat from combustion into mechanical energy (or power) is lower than the relative temperature difference

$$\eta_{Carnot} \leq \frac{T_{high} - T_{low}}{T_{low}} \quad (1)$$

The fuels necessary for generating such temperature difference can be of many types: petroleum, diesel, natural gas, syngas, producer gas (wood gas), ammonia, or hydrogen. There has been continued interest in using renewable energy carriers as automotive fuels, rather than fuels from fossil sources such as oil, coal and natural gas.

The reasons for this are manifold: (i) To be independent from foreign oil, (ii) to be independent from energy carriers which are depleted soon (50-500 years), (iii) to not anymore generate the greenhouse gas CO₂, (iv) for moving to a sustainable energy economy with renewable sources.

Using solar power, wind power and hydro/tidal power as primary and renewable energy sources would generally allow us to produce synthetic fuels, hydrocarbon fuels – for example by Fischer-Tropsch synthesis. Hydrogen as a fuel has been under scrutiny for over 50 years – to an extent that the term hydrogen economy was coined (Bockris 2002).

Regardless which fuel we use in combustion engines, we are fundamentally subject to Carnot’s limited efficiency. This limit is lifted however when we use instead the electro motoric force (EMF) from electrochemical cells such as batteries and fuel cells where the efficiency is defined as

$$\eta = \frac{W}{Q_{in}} \quad (2)$$

where W is the work which we can derive from the electrochemical reaction. W is for example the energy which we can derive from the electro motoric force (EMF) of a battery, fuel cell or dynamo (in Volts). Q is the enthalpy of formation in the chemical reaction.

Battery electric vehicles (EV) have been on the market since around 20 years. I remember very well when my supervisor in Berkeley, a well-known fuel cell and battery professor, gave me a ride in his Toyota hybrid car in the year 2001. The share of EV in the automotive market has been small but is steadily increasing. Energy storage is important for EV. Batteries and hydrogen are two energy storage concepts (Eberle 2010).

Batteries and fuel cells have in common that their electro motoric force EMF is generated by a pair of chemical constituents which constitutes a redox couple. In a lithium ion battery, this is for example the Li anode vs. the LiMn₂O₄ cathode which yields 3.05 V. The oxygen gas and hydrogen gas in the fuel cell yield an EMF of 1.23 V. This is not withstanding to the possibility to use hydrogen as a fuel in combustion engines (Pearson 2011). The advantage of a FC over a battery is that the former can continuously be fed by a gas container. This is the reason why the hydrogen tanks of a FCEV such as the Hyundai ix35 or the Toyota Mirai can be filled while you wash your hands

in the bathroom, whereas the charging of the battery of a Toyota Prius or Tesla Motors gives you plenty of time for a full lunch in the restaurant.

The number of electric charging stations for battery cars is quite large all over the world, whereas there is comparably little infrastructure for FCEV filling at this time (Eberle 2012). Toyota, Hyundai and Honda have recently brought FCEV on the market. I want to share my personal experience with a Hyundai ix35 FCEV during long distance trips, i.e. trips from Zürich to Berlin, to Luxembourg, Strassbourg and Bruxelles. A summary of trips is listed in Table 1 in the Appendix.

It is only since two or three years that FCEV are commercially available for everybody to buy. My employer maintains a garage with a pool of various cars and trucks. Some of them run on natural gas or have battery hybrid propulsion. Recently they bought a Hyundai ix35 Fuel Cell as part of a Swiss project on hydrogen mobility. Included in the project are two hydrogen filling stations; one at our Institute and one at a public gas station at Highway A1, operated by COOP Pronto, a Swiss grocery retailer.

Figure 1: The author pumping hydrogen in the Fuel Cell Electric Vehicle at the COOP Pronto gas station at Autobahn A1 in Hunzenschwil, Switzerland.

The hydrogen at our filling station is produced on-site by electrolysis of water with low cost vagabonding electricity from the grid. The hydrogen at COOP Pronto is delivered in gas bottles by trucks, also made from water electrolysis but with electric hydropower from a nearby river.

When I had to visit my colleague at a nearby institute 40 km away I decided to rent out our FCEV. I had some start-up problems with this new type of car. The car made no noise and therefore I was not sure whether it was able to drive or not. Eventually I could handle the car and drove off and found that it made no difference from any of the many other cars that I had driven in my more than 30 years driving experience.

Before I drove back home from the meeting, I decided to pay a visit to the COOP Pronto H2 filling station which happened to be nearby, “only” 25 km away. When I arrived at the H2 station, by guidance with the car’s navigation system, I identified after some seconds the H2 filling terminal. I parked my car, had a look at the terminal and decided to enter the store and ask for technical assistance. Together with the store assistant I then could handle the filling process and pay with my credit card at the terminal. This was a transaction in the amount of 12 Swiss Francs or Euros. Then I made it back to home.

Because of this overall pleasant experience I decided to make a longer trip with this FCEV the following week 22nd December 2016, as I had to participate in a PhD exam at EPFL in Lausanne, which is over 230 km away from Empa. I had been told that 450 km was a safe distance for this car to go on a filled tank but I figured I should take precautions with the amount of fuel available for the ride.

With internet search I found there was a H2 filling station near Lausanne at Marin from Belenos Clean Power, but I learnt they were moving the pumping station to Swisshydrogen in Fribourg; it was not yet available when I needed it. Other than that I was welcome to use it free of charge.

Hence I depended on following strategy. Driving from Empa to COOP Pronto, refill as much as possible, drive 190 km to Lausanne and 190 km back to COOP Pronto, which is 380 km in total. It should be no problem to drive this distance with one full tank in theory.

On the 22nd December when I started the FCEV, its navigation system somehow tried to keep me away from the highway. My negotiations with the navigation system cost me some time and some kilometers, and when I arrived at the COOP Pronto filling station, more time had passed than was necessary and available.

As I had become already very nervous over the lost time, I lost additional time and had to speed on the highway at the maximum allowed speed. I arrived 20 minutes late for the exam. Fortunately, I only missed the preparatory talk of the candidate, who was my PhD student. But I had made it at a relatively long distance with the FCEV and was looking forward to finish my long range travel with it the way back.

Eventually I found, when glancing at the dashboard, that the number of kilometers back to the COOP Pronto filling station was larger than the projected mileage based on my fuel consumption – which had been likely very high when I was speeding under pressure few hours before.

Now I was becoming even more nervous than on the morning because it looked like I was not going to make it to the filling station. So I slowed down and found that the cruise computer acknowledged my adjusted behavior by an adjustment of the projected mileage – towards my destination.

Yet, it took me considerable efforts to trim down my consumption so that the kilometers to drive and the mileage available would become equal. While I had been the fastest on the highway on the way to Lausanne, I drove now the slowest vehicle on the highway on the way back. Plus I switched off the warm air-conditioning although it was quite cold that December day.

The “empty tank” warning sign had been on for 50 kilometers and was flashing already when I finally arrived at very slow pace at the highway exit right before the COOP Pronto H2 filling station. I was almost frozen, but I was there. I started pumping and the pump stopped after few 100 grams of hydrogen were filled.

So, I asked for help inside the store and learnt the pump would always – in a first cycle - pre-pump in a minimum amount of gas when the tank of the vehicle was “almost empty”. It would then switch off and become ready for a new, second cycle. Sure the tank was “almost empty”, and I knew why. The

second filling cycle went smooth and I could continue my really exciting adventure that day back to home.

Reflecting over that trip I learnt what mistakes I had made. I wanted to access the highway, but the vehicle navigation system was programmed to drive over roads with low speed limits so that the consumption would be low and the mileage would be high. This is how you can make almost 600 km with one full tank. When you speed on highways, it may be only half that distance or even less.

But as a passionate car driver – I grew up in Germany between Nürburgring and Francorchamps – I felt satisfaction over such pioneering long distance with a car which supposedly was only acquired for making local travel. I showed that long distance travel was possible.

I want to emphasize that I am not an automotive engineer or anything similar. I am a Physicist who researches materials. Frequently I travel to synchrotron and neutron sources worldwide. My next synchrotron campaign was in Berlin and I would normally ship my scientific instruments to there by a professional carrier and travel there by plane.

Figure 2: Fuel Cell Electric Vehicle at the Brandenburg Gate in Berlin, Germany after long range trip from Zürich, Switzerland.

However, I sympathized with the idea to go to Berlin with the FCEV. After some search in the internet and a number of phone calls and email exchanges I held a CEP H2 Card in my hand which I could use in early 2017 to fill H2 in Germany at over a dozen filling stations.

Soon I found a route how to get from Zürich to Berlin; I took an intermediate fill behind the Swiss-German border from a newly established Shell H2 station,

then made it to the largest highway truck stop in Germany at the A3 which has a H2 filling station from French oil company Total. The 460 km from there to Shell H2 filling station at Heerstrasse in Berlin were safely made though at moderate speed. I had made it with cargo in the FCEV from Zürich to Berlin!

Figure 3: Screenshot of the cellphone app from H2 Mobility, showing the publicly available H2 filling stations of their network. The green circles show the stations which are currently in operation. The red ones show the non-operation stations because of failure, maintenance or business-hours shutdown.

I felt a deep satisfaction when paying a visit to the Brandenburg Gate with the FCEV. See for yourself in Figure 2.

During the two weeks synchrotron beamtime in Berlin I paid also a visit to H2 Mobility, a small spin off company from eleven global players in fossil

fuels, automotive industry and gas infrastructure technology. By 2023, H2 Mobility wants to operate 400 H2 gas stations in Germany alone. Their mobile phone app shows right now close to 60 H2 stations in Europe between Norway and Italy which are ready for public access now, most of them in Germany. My way from Berlin back to Switzerland was smooth but depended on whether I was moving very fast between two approximate H2 stations or driving very slow between two remote stations. The evolution of this dynamics will depend on the speed how fast new H2 stations are being built.

Since, I made business trips to Luxembourg, which was a small odyssey given that Wuppertal was the nearest available H2 station, 280 km away from Luxembourg. The way back to Wuppertal, an overall 560 km distance, was only possible by making a stop at the St@rt Hürth Chemie factory in Germany, who offered me a free 350 bar H2 filling service for the very few occasions when requested.

The FCEV cars are built with 700 bar H2 pressure tanks. The Hyundai accepts 5.4 kg H2 at this pressure for almost 600 km range. Half that pressure means half that filling level and thus only half the range. You see, therefore, that going with H2 through Europe at this time requires carefully planning and the luck to not become unlucky during the trip when a pump station fails.

I realized this on my trip to a conference in Strassbourg, where I wanted to make a necessary refill at the new Shell H2 station behind the Swiss-German border. When I arrived, I was told it broke down and I could not pump. There was already another FCEV waiting from the night before – a Toyota Mirai that came the long way from Austria.

I got nervous but I had to deliver an invited talk in Strassbourg and therefore could not spend much time with thinking. So I simply moved on to Strassbourg. I arrived later in Strassbourg than planned but just on time. After my talk I was calm enough to search for solutions to come back to home, preferably with the FCEV.

With internet access I found that the H2 station of the Fraunhofer Solar Institute in German Freiburg should be the station of choice. But it would close at 8 pm every day. I was not familiar with that station but supposedly my CEP card would work for filling there. I made sure I left Strassbourg on time and arrived indeed in Freiburg on time.

As I was busy with operating the terminal and attaching the pressure hose to the tank, I noticed another Hyundai ix35 Fuel Cell waiting behind me. The driver got out and asked “Are you happy with that car?” I answered “Yes, it’s doing great. It’s my new hobby.” The gentleman introduced himself as the general Hyundai dealer in Freiburg. We had a nice chat, and when it was his turn to pump, the pump went on strike.

While I had been lucky enough to get my car filled, still 180 km from home, The Hyundai dealer had to return to his nearby home in the city without getting the car filled. Weeks later I happened to have the Fraunhofer’s gas station technician on the phone, and I learnt that he had been on a weekend barbecue when the automatic dispatch call from that pump failure reached him. It was a frequently recurring software error. 24 minutes later, as he arrived at the pump, he could make the H2 pump work again.

Worthwhile to mention is here that the Fraunhofer hydrogen station in Freiburg is powered by solar PV panels. The hydrogen is produced by water electrolysis and all necessary power comes exclusively from the sun.

I made another trip to University of Darmstadt who had invited me for a presentation, and that one was a smooth ride without any unpleasant incident. Before returning to Zürich I had to decide: will I go the small risk with half full tank to the H2 Station in Freiburg, half way to Zürich. Or will I drive first 40 km North in opposite direction to the Air Liquide H2 Station in Offenbach for a full refill? I chose this 80 km extra way for the full refill.

My most recent long range trip was to Bruxelles. This was an overall 1800 km long way as I had to choose Air Liquide Düsseldorf in Germany for a final refill before Bruxelles. I had arranged that I would pick up my H2 filling card from Air Liquide, and thereafter I could pump in Bruxelles. And continue my way home to Germany and Switzerland. I filled up 7 times during this long trip.

Yesterday (17 March, 2018) I went again to Lausanne. For the way back, Swisshydrogen in Fribourg offered me a refill at 350 bar – free of charge. This was sufficient for the hassle free drive home to Zürich.

The CEO of Swisshydrogen drives a small Italian brand car which he and colleagues equipped with a fuel cell and a battery range extender. With 350 bar pressure they can fill its tank up sufficient for 400 to 425 km. All in all, that car drove 140,000 km with hydrogen.

It appears that the consumer can cope at large with a FCEV (Hardman 2016). You fill your FCEV at the H2 station conveniently like any other car. There is an industry which manufactures not only the FCEV but also the necessary infrastructure. And there are industry norms which make operation and handling

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safe (SAE 2016). The author of this position paper would definitely welcome a mobility landscape which runs individual and public traffic on hydrogen, preferably produced from renewable energy (Ginley 2016). A recent study shows that the overhaul of Germany's mobility infrastructure would cost over 60 billion Euros (Emonts 2017). Given that it is the Asian car manufacturers who are first on the market with FCEV – in Europe! – there is little doubt that Asia is sensing business in Europe: with the hydrogen economy (Chen 2017).

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APPENDIX

Table 1: Summary of trips within Switzerland and trips to Germany, France, Luxembourg and Belgium with the Fuel Cell Electric Vehicle. The destination cities are typed in bold letters. Zürich (Empa Dübendorf) is the city of departure and return where hydrogen was filled at 700 bar prior to each journey. All other cities denote the H2 filling stations. Geisingen with double strike through means the H2 station was out of order that particular day.

	Depart										Return	km
1	Zürich	Villigen PSI	Hunzenschwil								Zürich	114
2	Zürich	Hunzenschwil	Lausanne	Hunzenschwil							Zürich	466
3	Zürich	Basel									Zürich	182
4	Zürich	Geisingen									Zürich	165
5	Zürich	Geisingen	Geiselwind	Berlin	Berlin	Geiselwind	Geisingen				Zürich	2000
6	Zürich	Geisingen	Offenbach	Hürth	Wuppertal	Luxembourg	Hürth	Wuppertal	Offenbach	Geisingen	Zürich	1900
7	Zürich	Geisingen	Strasbourg	Freiburg i. Br.							Zürich	450
8	Zürich	Freiburg i. Br.	Darmstadt	Offenbach		Freiburg i. Br.					Zürich	860
9	Zürich	Geisingen	Offenbach	Düsseldorf		Bruxelles	Wuppertal	Offenbach	Geisingen		Zürich	1900
10	Zürich		Lausanne	Fribourg FR							Zürich	480